

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCIES OF 8TH-9TH GRADE STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article addresses the emergence of new meanings in the global education system through the discipline of technology, the process of organizing technology lessons within the general education system based on competency-oriented approaches, the requirements imposed on it, the challenges encountered in activities aimed at shaping students' technological competencies in technology classes, and their solutions.*

Keywords: *society, technology, competence, modern production, education system, effectiveness, profitability, motivation, transformational activity, industry, method, issue, quality, result.*

Introduction

Technological competencies formed at school do not sufficiently meet the requirements imposed on them. If we analyze the readiness of schoolchildren to master technological competencies, that is: their direct inclusion in the transformative activity that is the basis of these competencies, then there is a lack of clear ideas about its essence, structure, and evidence-based recommendations for the development of technological competencies. The development of technological competencies in students is associated with the mastery of various types of practical activities. During our research, the following methodological foundations for the effective development of technological competencies in students in grades 8-9 were identified: introducing various technologies for processing materials into the content of educational activities; implementing the educational process under the guidance of a teacher with priority given to the student's independent work; organizing the practical activities of students on the basis of the unity of the processes of learning technologies and the preparation of objects; combining individual and collective forms of working with objects in classes; directing teaching methods to activate the independent activity of students; To arouse students' interest in searching for alternative technologies and methods of making objects and to apply methods for its development.

The results of the study of the development patterns of general secondary education indicate the need to analyze the experiences of leading educational institutions in our country and improve the opportunities and conditions for developing technological competencies in schoolchildren in the context of the tasks of transition to a new educational paradigm. In conditions of limited resource provision for the development of technological competencies in schoolchildren, its evolutionary development becomes more complicated, and the achievement of a new quality level of the system is determined by the level of scientific and methodological development and normative coordination of processes. This determines the role and importance of the development of a modern model of the system for the development of technological competencies in schoolchildren and the organizational, pedagogical and personnel conditions for its implementation.

Since competencies are a complex, integral education, their development is impossible without comprehensive planning of the activities of teachers and students, without choosing the most appropriate tools for implementing this process. In fact, the development of a methodology for developing competencies will be ineffective if there is no clear idea of the process of their formation, taking into account many factors. A way to solve this problem can be modeling, the purpose of which is to create a general idea of how to more effectively develop students' subject competencies in basic general education, in our case we are talking about technological competencies.

In technology lessons, it was possible to create a unique system for developing technological competencies in students of grades 8-9 and develop its structural and functional components, as well as to identify and implement pedagogical conditions for its implementation. The main goal of creating a system for developing technological competencies in students and implementing it is to develop in them technological and personally significant qualities, needs and interests, values, motives for practical activity, and most importantly, technological skills.

The main task of the system for developing technological competencies in students in grades 8-9 is to develop a culture of technological thinking in students (to form an adequate idea of the essence of technological phenomena and their interrelationships, to develop the ability to reason on technological issues, to analyze specific technological situations, to gain practical technological experience); to ensure the social adaptation of students to the changes taking place at the current stage of the development of our society and their ability to find their way in it, as well as to increase their basic technological knowledge necessary for their future technological activities; to form practical skills in making responsible technological decisions; to teach them to self-improvement, develop the ability to learn independently, to be proactive and active. 8th -9th grade students are:

- 1) the social order of society to prepare students for technological activities;
- 2) The goal is to prepare students for technological activities in a social order;
- 3) The level of development of technological competencies in students in grades
- 4) Practical results of the system for developing technological competencies in 8th-9th grade students.

It should be noted that the feasibility of our development of technological competencies in students of grades 8-9 is determined by the achievement of certain results. Therefore, its purpose is manifested as a system-forming component. The systematic approach we used to create a system for developing technological competencies in students and forming technological skills based on a theoretical methodological approach allows not only to study the structural components of the system, but also to describe its functional connections and relationships. All of the above functional components of the system for forming technological practical knowledge and skills in students and developing their technological competencies are integrally and closely related to each other. Having analyzed pedagogical, psychological and other special literature, we tried to consider in our work the technological competence of schoolchildren as an integral part of professional skills. Competence, which includes motivational, organizational and control abilities, as well as personal qualities that help to involve school children in transformational activities based on a certain algorithm of actions. The development of technological competence of students in secondary schools is planned through the development and testing of an educational model, the creation of certain conditions in technology lessons and extracurricular activities.

At the initial stage of the implementation of the educational model, students develop the ability to express their activities in the form of algorithms on the example of processes known and familiar to them; learn to read, transform and present information in various forms and formats (graphs, tables, clusters, diagrams, graphic symbols, etc.). At the second stage, the ability to change, improve technology in new or given conditions is formed through the practical mastery of creative search methods for solutions (jigsaw, simulation and virtual laboratories, design). At the final stage, it is planned to achieve a level of subjective activity of students, that is, independently determine the relevance, necessity, and demand of new technology, master the basics of engineering. An integrated approach to solving problems, manifestation of activity, independence and readiness for professional self-determination. The implementation of this stage is carried out by adapting the elements of the professional career planning strategy.

The target block of the model embodies the ideal image of technological competence and its development. The purpose of this model is to achieve a high level of development of technological competence of students in technology lessons according to the State Educational Standard. It becomes the main integrative characteristic of students, which includes cognitive, operational-activity, personal and axiological components and reflects the level of development of professional knowledge, skills and professionally important qualities in connection with the subsequent professional activity of students. Along with this, the student's internal desire to maximize self-realization in educational activities increases. Intensive use of subject integration in the education system aimed at professional training and socialization of students requires knowledge of a group of specialties from subject teachers, not a narrow range of knowledge. The methodology for developing technological competencies of students in grades 8-9 plays an important role in modern educational processes. Through the use of technology, students of this age not only hone practical skills, but also expand and deepen their knowledge in various subjects. The main methods of the methodology we offer are:

1. Interactive lessons - conducting lessons using multimedia tools and online platforms. (Open educational platform "Edx-course")
2. Project-based learning - students work individually and in groups on small projects (Jigsaw, simulation), which allows them to apply technologies in practice.
3. Experiments - conducting various laboratory work to practically test the capabilities of technologies. (Virtual laboratories)
4. Online resources – students learn using various resources on the internet. (ChatGPT)

Recommended tools for developing technological competencies :

- Programming languages (e.g. Python, Scratch)
- Robotics kits
- Online learning platforms (e.g. Khan Academy)

The use of pedagogical technologies in the process of developing students' technological competencies is important for making the learning process effective and interactive. Below are the types of pedagogical technologies used in the development of students' technological competencies during our study and their advantages:

The Jigsaw method is an interactive teaching method based on working with small groups, aimed at developing students' abilities to work together and learn from each other.

How does the Jigsaw method work?

Dividing the topic : the teacher divides the lesson topic into several parts. For example, each group member divides the topics or sub-sections that will be discussed in the lesson. Forming groups : students are divided into small groups (3-4 people). Each member must read and understand the section assigned to him, because later he will explain this topic to his group.

Expert groups: Students who have studied a similar topic are grouped into small groups called “expert groups.” Together, they study the topic in detail, discuss it, and explain it to each other.

Return to group: Each student returns to their original group and explains what they have learned to the rest of the group. Since each student is an expert on their assigned topic, they build the group's collective knowledge.

General discussion and presentation: Group members learn from each other and try to fully understand the topic. At the end, each group makes a presentation about their work and results. Advantages of the Jigsaw method: each student is an important part of the group, and if he does not explain his part, the other members cannot fully understand. This ensures the active participation of each student.

Interdependence: Students become interdependent because everyone has to share their knowledge with others. This fosters teamwork and mutual support.

Increased interest and motivation: Students find it more interesting and responsible because they are required to independently learn a section and then explain this knowledge to others. Developing critical and analytical thinking: Students need to have a good understanding of the topics they are studying in order to analyze them in depth and explain them correctly to others. When planning lessons : the teacher should divide the topic into parts and distribute it to the students. The division of the topic into parts should be based on scientific logic.

When managing groups: Every student in the group should be an equal participant.

Each student must contribute so that no student is left out.

In assessment: the jigsaw method assesses not only students' individual learning, but also their cooperation within the group and their ability to correctly explain knowledge to each other. The Jigsaw method ensures that students work collaboratively and actively participate in the learning process.

Grade 8: “ Technology and Design” section (3rd quarter)

Topic: Making a decorative clock from wood

1. Lesson Objective: - to provide students with practical skills in woodworking and making products from it , and to learn how to work with tools and equipment used in woodworking. - develop knowledge sharing skills by teaching others information about an independently completed practical assignment.

2. Pending results: During the implementation of the new practical task, students independently learn the technology of making decorative wooden clocks and thereby acquire the skills to demonstrate the product they have made. They learn to verbally describe the quality and cost of the product, gain an understanding of entrepreneurship. They are able to analyze the shortcomings that were introduced during the process of making the product .

3. Lesson format: interactive lesson, using the Jigsaw method.

4. Teaching method: Jigsaw method, working in groups, sharing information and making presentations. 5. Lesson equipment :

Interactive whiteboard, posters, markers, tools and equipment used in woodworking, projector (if necessary).

Lesson stages:

1. Organizational part (Part 5):

students for the lesson and dividing them into groups.

- assign tasks to each group:

Group 1: provide information about woodworking and the equipment used in it Group 2:

Prepare a design for a decorative wooden clock and calculate the raw materials needed.

Group 3: Cutting, planing, burning, and finishing the wood for a decorative wooden clock.

2. Independent study of the topic (15 minutes) - Each group performs the assigned task independently.

- group members and prepared for presentation.

3. Organizing expert groups (10 minutes):

- One student from each group goes to the other group and explains the topic they have learned. In this way, all group members learn about each other's topics.

- Each student returns to their group, shares their newly learned information with their classmates, and prepares for the presentation.

4. Group presentation (20 minutes):

- Each group will make a presentation on their practical assignment.

- Other groups can ask questions and get additional information.

5. Summarize and conclude the lesson (10 minutes)

- After each group presentation, the teacher summarizes the topic and draws conclusions about the topic.

- a brief discussion of the social significance of the topic and ways to solve problems.

6. Homework: Students will prepare a short written analysis at home on a topic of their choice to gather additional information and explore the topic in more depth.

Conclusion

Based on the results, a conclusion is drawn about the development of technological competencies in students of grades 8-9. Based on the applied methodology and technologies, the possibilities of assessing the level of development of teachers' technological competencies were revealed by coordinating the assessment criteria and indicators. Based on real conditions, an opportunity was created for students to creatively solve one or another technical solution in the process of practical work, create or improve an item in the production process. As a result, the achievement of a high level of development of technological competencies in students of grades 8-9 of general secondary education schools was scientifically substantiated.

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